

http://plugin03.marketingdigitaltools.com/

NOVO TESTE

```

1 <!doctype html>
2 <html lang="pt-PT" prefix="og: http://ogp.me/ns#">
3
4 <head>
5     <meta charset="UTF-8">
6     <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, in
7     <link rel="profile" href="https://gmpg.org/xfn/11">
8
9
10 <!-- Search Engine Optimization by Rank Math - https://s.rank
11 <title>marketingdigitaltools.com - Marketing Digital Tools</ti
12 <meta name="robots" content="index, follow, max-snippet:-1, max-v
13 <link rel="canonical" href="http://plugin03.marketingdigitalto
14 <meta property="og:locale" content="pt_PT">
15 <meta property="og:type" content="website">
16 <meta property="og:title" content="marketingdigitaltools.com -
17 <meta property="og:url" content="http://plugin03.marketingdigi
18 <meta property="og:site_name" content="Marketing Digital Tools
19 <meta property="og:updated_time" content="2020-02-04T12:22:30+
20 <meta property="fb:admins" content="https://www.facebook.com/r
21 <meta property="og:image" content="http://plugin03.marketingdi
22 <meta property="og:image:width" content="463">
23 <meta property="og:image:height" content="330">
24 <meta property="og:image:alt" content="Logo Marketing Digital
25 <meta property="og:image:type" content="image/png">
26 <meta name="twitter:card" content="summary_large_image">
27 <meta name="twitter:title" content="marketingdigitaltools.com
28 <meta name="twitter:site" content="@mktdigitaltools">
29 <meta name="twitter:creator" content="@mktdigitaltools">
30 <meta name="twitter:image" content="http://plugin03.marketing
31 <script type="application/ld+json">{"@context":"https://\sche
32 <script type="application/ld+json">{"@context":"https://\sche
33 <meta name="google-site-verification" content="sQBJ98u1EC3V5-8
34 <!-- /Rank Math WordPress SEO plugin -->
35 <link rel='dns-prefetch' href='//s.w.org' />
36 <link rel="alternate" type="application/rss+xml" title="Market
37 <link rel="alternate" type="application/rss+xml" title="Market
38 <script type="text/javascript">
39     window._wpemojiSettings = {"baseUrl":"https://\s.
40     !function(e,a,t){var r,n,o,i,p=a.createElement("c
41 </script>
42 <style type="text/css">
43 img.wp-smiley,
44 img.emoji {
45     display: inline !important;
46     border: none !important;
47     box-shadow: none !important;
48     height: 1em !important;
49     width: 1em !important;
50     margin: 0 .07em !important;
51     vertical-align: -0.1em !important;
52     background: none !important;
53     padding: 0 !important;
54 }
55 </style>
56 <link rel='stylesheet' id='wp-block-library-css' href='ht
57 <link rel='stylesheet' id='wc-block-style-css' href='http://p
58 <link rel='stylesheet' id='dashicons-css' href='http://plugi
59 <link rel='stylesheet' id='everest-forms-general-css' href='f
60 <link rel='stylesheet' id='woocommerce-layout-css' href='htt
61 <link rel='stylesheet' id='woocommerce-smallscreen-css' href=
62 <link rel='stylesheet' id='woocommerce-general-css' href='htt
63 <style id='woocommerce-inline-inline-css' type='text/css'>
64 .woocommerce form .form-row .required { visibility: visible; }
65 </style>
66 <link rel='stylesheet' id='font-awesome-css' href='http://pl
67 <link rel='stylesheet' id='zakra-style-css' href='http://plu
    
```

Detetado em Website

0 ERROS 0 AVISOS 2 ITENS

Website	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	1 ITEM
ID: http://plugin03.marketingdigitaltools.com/#website					
ProfessionalService	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS			1 ITEM
@id			http://plugin03.marketingdigitaltools.com/#website		
url			http://plugin03.marketingdigitaltools.com/		
name			Marketing Digital Tools		
potentialAction					
@type			SearchAction		
target					
@type			EntryPoint		
urlTemplate			http://plugin03.marketingdigitaltools.com/?s={search_term_string}		
query-input					
@type			PropertyValueSpecification		
valueRequired			http://schema.org/True		
valueName			search_term_string		